

NEW EDUCATION POLICY 2020 & IT'S IMPACT ON SOCIETY

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Introduction:

“English education is the Tigris's milk, the one who will drink it will not be without roaring.”

Dr.B.R .Ambedkar

The Union Government has launched the New National Education policy- 2020 on July 29, 2020. NEP2020 is based on the premise that only knowledge can transform our society from stagnation and poverty to dynamism and prosperity, from marginalization and deprivation to empowerment and recognition, from ignorance and delusion to enlightenment and liberation and from conflict and intolerance to peaceful co-existence and nonviolence. This is the “Dream Project” of the union government “making India a global knowledge superpower which will be completed in the year 2040. The NEP-2020 is meant to provide an enlightening vision and compendious framework for both school and higher education across the country and the Indian education system will become closer to international standard.

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Basic features in the School Policy

The government has introduced vocational and polytechnic education for school students through the new policy under the title ‘Reimagining vocational education’, which aims to remove the hard separation between academic and vocational streams. Vocational subjects will be introduced early as early as grade 6, including internship opportunities from grades 6 to 12. This however ignores the importance of ensuring basic mainstream education to all students till at least grade 10. Students opting for such courses will certainly not be from privileged backgrounds. Children who are economically backward and belonging to lower rungs of people who struggled in English, coding, etc would end up opting for these streams. Introducing this at such an early age will form a barrier for first-generation learners and those from disadvantaged backgrounds to access higher education.

The NEP2020 aims at universalization of education in India with a 100% Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) by 2030 for school education. The policy has a target of 50% GER in higher education by 2035 which is currently at 26.3% at school level, this will assist in bringing approximately 2 crore children who are currently out of school back in to the mainstream. 3.5 crore seats will be added in higher education. It also aims to increase the public investment in the Education sector to reach 6 percent of GDP at the earliest. School governance is set to change, with a new accreditation framework and an independent authority to regulate both public and private schools. In the reality Madhyapradesh government has been closed 9000 school. Central govt gave permission to open the school to the company. It means that students will become a raw product for a company. The main aim of companization of the school is that student become a job worker for company. There will be fight between Govt. school and company school and in this war govt. school cannot live.

The NEP2020 education policy recommends that the curriculum and pedagogy of our institutions must our institutions must develop among the students a deep sense of respect towards the fundamental duties and constitutional values ,national bonding and a conscious awareness of one’s roles and responsibilities in a changing world. On the other hand RSS Joint secretary Bhaiyya Joshi said that “RSS main aim is that to finish the Indian constitution and formed law of Manusmrity depends upon Varna System” .In the varna system only Brahmin can be enjoyed all the supremacy power..Therefore in the next coming year only 15% students of upper class can be learned and 85% will become only a Balutedar.

Value Based Education-

NEP2020 in section 11 emphasizes value based education for development of humanistic, ethical, cultural, Constitutional and universal human values of truth, righteous conduct (dharma),peace, love, nonviolence ,scientific temper, citizenship values and life skills but unfortunately not much was done by HE institutions to implement it’s suggestions. NEP 2020aims to facilitate an inclusive, participatory and holistic approach, which takes into consideration field experiences, empirical research stakeholder feedback, as well as lessons learned from best practices.It is a progressive shift towards a more scientific approach to education. The prescribed structure will help to cater the ability of the child stages of cognitive development as social and physical awareness. If implemented in its true vision, the new structure can at par with the leading counties of the world.When NEP 2020 set a goal for value based education .But whichr religion’s values are important for this NEP2020.Only Hinduism! If you want to become an engineer then there is no need to learn Physics,Chemistry,Math or other basic subject of science. Students can choose Vedas ,Puranas and any other from 14 subject. What kind of engineer will he become.?

Admission Process

The National Testing Agency will introduce a pilot version of the common entrance test by Dec.2020,which will be used for admission to all IOES and central universities in 2021.Some Indian Institutes of Technology are working on developing the technical structure of the Academic Credit Bank ,which will also be established by December and become applicable to all new students joining central universities next year.

Structure of Autonomous college

Central govt.has clearly indicates that in the upcoming year all the education system becomes public or private property. IT also paves the way for foreign universities to set up campuses in India.

The process of converting affiliated colleges into degree granting autonomous institutions and then further into fully fledged universities is estimated to take at least 15 years, as the centre will have to provide financial assistance for this purpose. The ministry thinks that an increase in government funding of education to 6% of GDP will be sufficient to cover the financial implications of the NEP. Currently, India spends around 4.6 percent of its total GDP on education. However such an increase in funding has been propose but not achieved for the last half century. Nowadays current GDP of India is -32 then how can be India spend6% GDP on education.?

The policy also calls for the rejuvenation, active promotion, and support of private philanthropic activity in the education sector. In particular, over and above the public budgetary support which would have been otherwise provided to them, any public institution can take initiatives towards raising private philanthropic funds to enhance educational experiences. The matter of commercialization of education has been dealt with by the policy through multiple relevant fronts, including: the light it tight regulatory approach that mandates full public self-disclosure of finances ,procedures,

course and program offering and educational outcomes; the substantial investment in public education and mechanisms for good governance of all institutions, public and private. In this new education policy It emphasizes setting up of Gender Inclusion Fund, Special Education Zones for disadvantaged regions and groups. This educational institution may take low rate land from the poor people.

Under the new policy, private and self-governed colleges will receive more autonomy. When these colleges hand out certificates unchecked, corporatism may follow. This will create a situation where higher studies become a privilege only for those who can afford it. A centralized education system will amount to a stepping stone to social exclusion and dilution of the Right to Education act. The government stated that it is proposing to improve the quality and autonomy of higher education, however, in a completely backward move; it is dismantling the University Grants Commission (UGC) which was a core structural and regulatory body for higher education. This will only accelerate the commodification and centralization of education.

Organizations and institutions when vested with educational structure and financial autonomy will be enabled to create additional courses and departments. However, without funding from government bodies, institutions will naturally turn to the students. The tuition fee will substantially increase, not just for students in that particular department, but all the students attending the institution. This coupled with another feature offered by the NEP, i.e., multiple exit options at universities will increase the dropout rates. Under the multiple exit and entry option, if a student decides to leave mid-course, he/she will receive appropriate certification for credits earned until the point which will be digitally stored in an Academic Bank of Credit (ABC). A 'certificate', a 'diploma' a 'Bachelor's Degree with Research' respectively will be awarded for each year of a four-year course. With financial autonomy resulting in financial burden on students and availability of certification each year, more students will be prompted to dropout. This creates an immense disparity between financially able and disabled students. Financially better-off students will get higher chances for studies and be able to acquire better opportunities. This would again amount to dilution of the Right to Education act.

It emphasizes setting up of Gender Inclusion Fund, Special Education Zones for disadvantaged regions and groups. The management/administration of the proposed 'multidisciplinary HEIs/clusters involving Open Distance Learning (ODL)' programs and credit transfer in credit bank itself is a huge task considering the number of students. The role of the 'National Education Technology Forum' is very significant here and much depends on its efficiency and accountability. (Today, the customers of nationalized banks cannot get their pass-books duly filled in by the banks in time)

The time tables of a multidisciplinary HEIs/cluster and those of the other HEIs here students have to go for taking lessons of the subjects of their choice require appropriate matching. The top central bureaucracy does not understand the difficulties faced by the time table committees of present HEIs. The issue seems to be trivial but the principles know how complex is the matter. Scanty infrastructure and multidisciplinary subject options may be a circus for HEIs. Granting autonomy, with 'graded' system, to all the HEIs involves merger of single faculty HEIs into multidisciplinary HEIs/clusters. The suitable mechanism for that is yet to be evolved. The process of granting autonomy to colleges is the process of relieving the affiliating universities of the burden of their colleges. That involves the problem of the placement of the excess university employees in the equivalent posts in the multidisciplinary HEIs or in the bureaucratic hierarchy of the regulatory bodies. That is a big task that involves grievances, disputes and settlements in an appropriate manner. This is an issue concerning employees in about 900+ universities in India.

Nature of Appoint of industrial Representative.

NEP-2020 plans to appoint government, alumni and industry representatives on the BOGs and HEIs. There will not be any problem if they have only advisory role. But the NEOP-20 has given them powers of governance and that is a big issue. There are 55 central universities the crown jewels of Indian HE system. Recently, six vice-chancellors of central universities have been sacked; another 5 have been charge sheeted. In reality it is a crisis of accountability. Surprisingly, each of the 55 universities is governed by a separate act. The selection, appointments and functions of the central university authorities is a matter of research and urgent reformation (Mehta, 2020). SO the autonomy and control of The BOGs is and will be a matter of debate in and outside of parliament. All this representative will be taken from only RSS.

CONCLUSION

In india more than 32 crore people living under below poverty line. In this Corona pandemic period 80% people become jobless .Then How this people can afford such costly institute?The NEP 2020 policy will seemingly increase the economic divide in a country that is already divided by religion, caste, gender and wealth. It may make it nearly impossible for disadvantaged classes to climb up the social ladder. It is very dangerous to SC,ST,OBC,Minority, and under privileged people and their next generation will become only bondage labour .Therefore all the people of india must fight against this NEP2020.

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